

GOLD LEACHING FROM MOLYBDENITE CONCENTRATE IN NITRIC ACID AND HYPOCHLORITE ELECTROLYTES

Rasulova S.N.¹

Guro V.P.²

Ibragimov A.B.³

Adinayev Kh.F.⁴

¹⁻²⁻³⁻⁴Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, Tashkent city

E-mail: sitora_r91@mail.ru

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The sulfide phase of ore minerals is subject to passivation under the oxidizing conditions of hydrometallurgy. Overcoming it is achieved by a relative increase in the Redox potential [1,2] due to the oxidizing reagent. For molybdenite concentrate (MoC), HNO₃, NaClO are used. It is easier to generate hypochlorite in the MOC pulp (10% NaCl, H₂O, Na₂CO₃) with anodic polarization of a carbon electrode. The product yield depends on the concentration of NaCl, stirring, T: L-ratio, anode potential, temperature, current density, slightly - on pH. When the solution is acidified, MoO₃•(H₂O) x is precipitated (together with Re). The low emission of chlorine from the electrolyzer at pH 10 allows the process to be considered environmentally friendly, and leaching is the result of the interaction of IOC with chlorine, and not with the charge transferred from the anode.

Purpose of the work: data on the kinetics of leaching in nitric acid and hypochlorite electrolytes of molybdenite (Almalyk) and gold-bearing (Kokpatas) sulfide concentrates for the development of hydrometallurgical bases for their processing.

Mo concentrate (grinding 0.074 mm; composition,%: 38 Mo, 0.7 Re; 2.5 Cu; 0.009 P; 0.025 Sb; 0.05 WO₃; 25.2 S; 10.8 SiO₂; 0 , 42 H₂O), Kokpatas concentrate (grinding 0.074 mm; composition - pyrite and arsenopyrite: 90-97% of sulfides).

Leaching units were used: powders, rotating disk electrodes from pressed powders, with control of the results by methods of gravimetry, electrochemical measurements, and elemental analysis. Active chlorine NaClO was determined according to GOST 18190-72 iodometrically, active free chlorine (a, c) - by titration with methyl orange.

Comparison of the kinetics of leaching of MoC in nitric acid (HNO₃ 25%) and hypochlorite (a.kh. 12%) electrolytes at 22 and 35 ° C is carried out: the choice of temperature is due to the thermal stability of hypochlorite; revealed a twofold relative advantage of the second of them. The selected mode of leaching of Kokpatas sulfide ore in an aerated solution based on HNO₃ with background,%:

H₂SO₄ 5; 24 oC. The limiting stage of the process of dissolution of MOC in a hypochlorite solution was revealed, the diffusion coefficients were calculated $D=5,06 \cdot 10^{-8}$, $4,96 \cdot 10^{-6}$, at 45 °C and rotation speed, ω , rpm: 700, 1800, respectively ; and diffusion activation energy $E_{act} = 8518.4, 10667.5$

As a result, basing on powder samples of sulfide concentrates from molybdenite ores and ores of the Kokpatas deposit, as well as compact rotating disk electrodes made from them, in nitrate aerated and hypochlorite leaching solutions, the regularities of their oxidation have been revealed. The process of their dissolution in an oxidizing media takes place under diffusion control.

References:

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